

**Internet Usage of the High School Students of a
Filipino Chinese School in Iloilo City, Philippines**

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Abstract

Nowadays, everybody seems to know the various benefits offered by the Internet. The value of its utilization, however, depends on one's preference. This study aimed to determine the utilization of Internet by the high school students of Hua Siong College of Iloilo, Inc., Philippines. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions: 1) is there a significant relationship between sex and hours spent with the Internet?, 2) is there a significant relationship between sex and purpose of using the Internet, 3) is there a significant relationship between year level and hours spent with the Internet?, 4) is there a significant relationship between year level and purpose of using the Internet?, and 5) is there a significant relationship between hours spent with the Internet and the purpose of using the Internet? Cluster sampling method was utilized, in which one section per year level was randomly chosen. Quantitative-descriptive design was employed in this study. No significant relationships were found between sex and hours spent with the Internet, year level and hours spent in the Internet, year level and purpose of using the Internet, and hours spent with the Internet and purpose of using the Internet. However, a significant relationship was found between sex and purpose of using the Internet. Female students are likely to use the Internet for academics or social networking purposes; while, male student are inclined to use the Internet for online gaming.

Keywords: Internet, Internet use, online gaming, social networking, academics

Introduction

The internet is a global network of computers, which enables these computers to send small packets of digital data among each other (WebWise Team, 2012). Internet serves as another medium for transferring information (Duffy, 2000). It is now part of our world, which allows every person to use it for doing school projects, maintaining relationships with distant friends, and playing games.

Brandstrom (2011) found that teachers consider Internet as a valuable source of information and an additional teaching tool to motivate students, make teaching more fun, and allow variation in teaching. Moreover, Luanan, Nawi, Nadzri, and Rom (2013), discovered that Internet had a substantial impact on the daily life of the students as their study revealed that majority of their respondents admitted using the Internet in their academic and in daily life.

Despite the advantages of the Internet, its usage becomes a problem when misused. Misusing the benefits of the Internet begins to cause a decline in terms of what healthy adolescents are expected to achieve, such as maintaining grades and school attendance, participating in family life, and keeping up friendships outside of cyberspace. Internet may cause distraction, procrastination, and plagiarism (Luaran et al., 2013).

Parents tend to worry about their children watching too much television or spending too much time on the phone. Now, parents also have to be aware of how much time their kids spend with the Internet and the purposes of using the Internet. Luaran et al. (2013) found that most of the students use the Internet every day and they use it for assignment, information searching, communication, downloading, and others.

Recognizing the advantages and disadvantages of using the Internet, this study was conducted involving high school students of Hua Siong College of Iloilo, Inc.

Formerly known as Iloilo Central Commercial High School, Hua Siong College of Iloilo is an educational institution located on Iznart Street, Iloilo City, Philippines. It was founded by the Filipino Chinese Chamber of Commerce of Iloilo (Hua Siong College of Iloilo, Inc., 2015). It caters pre-elementary, elementary, high school, and college education.

Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of the study. The independent variables were sex and year level, while the dependent variables were hours spent in the Internet and purpose of using the Internet.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the study

Statement of the Problem and Hypotheses

This study aimed to determine the utilization of Internet by the high school students of Hua Siong College of Iloilo, Inc., Philippines. Specifically, this study aimed to answer the following questions.

- 1) Is there a significant relationship between sex and hours spent with the Internet?

- 2) Is there a significant relationship between sex and purpose of using the Internet?
- 3) Is there a significant relationship between year level and hours spent with the Internet?
- 4) Is there a significant relationship between year level and purpose of using the Internet?
- 5) Is there a significant relationship between hours spent with the Internet and the purpose of using the Internet?

In line with the problems, the following null hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

- 1) There is no significant relationship between sex and hours spent with the Internet.
- 2) There is no significant relationship between sex and purpose of using the Internet.
- 3) There is no significant relationship between year level and hours spent with the Internet.
- 4) There is no significant relationship between year level and purpose of using the Internet.
- 5) There is no significant relationship between hours spent with the Internet and the purpose of using the Internet.

Methodology

This study utilized the quantitative-descriptive research design.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study were the 112 high school students of Hua Siong College of Iloilo who were officially enrolled during the academic year 2014-2015. They were chosen through cluster sampling method choosing one section only per year level. The drawing of lots resulted the following: Section Lanozes from Grade 7, Section Mahogany from Grade 8, Section Narra from Grade 9, and Section Jasmin from 4th Year.

Table 1
Distribution of Respondents

Category	n	%
Entire Group	112	100
Sex		
Female	61	54
Male	51	46
Year Level		
Grade 7	31	28
Grade 8	31	28
Grade 9	26	23
4 th Year	24	21

Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents. In terms of sex, 54% were female while 46% were male. As to year level, 28% were Grade 7, also 28% were Grade 8, 23% were Grade 9, while 21% were 4th Year.

Instrumentation

To determine students' usage of the Internet, the researchers prepared a questionnaire. Respondents ticked the corresponding button for their answers.

The questionnaire was composed of three (3) parts: student-related factor, hours spent (average per day), and purpose. Student-related factors included the sex and year level. Hours spent (average per day) was categorized into less than 2 hours, 2-3 hours, and more than 3 hours. Lastly, the purpose was classified as social networking, online gaming, and academic research.

Data Analysis

Chi-square was utilized to determine the relationship between variables covered in this study.

Results and Discussion

Relationship between Sex and Purpose

Table 2 shows the observation in the number of hours spent with the Internet between female and male students.

Table 2
Sex and Hours Spent Crosstabulation

Sex	< 2 hours	2-3 hours	> 3 hours
Female	12	14	35
Male	8	13	30

Applying the Pearson Chi-Square test, no significant relationship was found between sex and hours spent with the Internet, $\chi(2)=0.331$, $p=0.847$.

Relationship between Sex and Purpose

Table 3 shows the observation in the purposes of using the Internet between female and male students.

Table 3
Sex and Purpose Crosstabulation

Sex	Online Gaming	Academic Research	Social Networking
Female	2 _a	11 _b	48 _b
Male	33 _a	8 _b	10 _b

Using the Pearson Chi-Square test, significant relationship was found between sex and purpose of using the Internet, $\chi(2)=52.352, p=0.000$.

Relationship between Sex and Purpose

Table 4 shows the observation in the number of hours spent with the Internet among year levels.

Table 4
Year Level and Hours Spent Crosstabulation

Sex	< 2 hours	2-3 hours	> 3 hours
Grade 7	7	8	16
Grade 8	4	7	20
Grade 9	4	6	16
4 th Year	5	6	13

Utilizing the Pearson Chi-Square test, no significant relationship was found between year level and hours spent with the Internet, $\chi(6)=52.352, p=0.947$.

Relationship between Sex and Purpose

Table 5
Year Level and Purpose Crosstabulation

Sex	Online Gaming	Academic Research	Social Networking
Grade 7	13	6	12
Grade 8	10	4	17
Grade 9	5	3	18
4 th Year	7	6	11

Table 5 shows the observation in the purposes of using the Internet among year levels.

Making use of the Pearson Chi-Square test, no significant relationship was found between year level and purpose of using the Internet, $\chi(6)=6.920$, $p=0.328$.

Relationship between Sex and Purpose

Table 6 shows the observation in the purposes of using the Internet among the hours spent in the Internet.

Table 6
Hours Spent and Purpose Crosstabulation

Category	Online Gaming	Academic Research	Social Networking
< 2 hours	7	5	8
2-3 hours	10	3	14
> 3 hours	18	11	36

Applying the Pearson Chi-Square test, no significant relationship was found between hours spent in the Internet and purpose of using the Internet, $\chi(4)=2.648$, $p=0.618$.

Conclusions

There is no significant relationship between sex and hours spent with the Internet. Hours spent in the Internet may vary regardless of sex. Any student may spend in the Internet for any number of hours.

There is a significant relationship between sex and purpose of using the Internet. Female students are likely to use the Internet for academics or social networking purposes; while, male students are inclined into using the Internet for online gaming.

There is no significant relationship between year level and hours spent with the Internet. Hours spent with the Internet may vary regardless of year level. Year level is not associated to a student's time spent in the Internet.

There is no significant relationship between year level and purpose of using the Internet. Regardless of year level, a student may use the Internet for online gaming, academic research, or social networking.

There is no significant relationship between hours spent with the Internet and purpose of using the Internet. Whether a student utilizes the Internet for online gaming, academic research, or social networking, number of hours spent may last for any number of hours in a day.

Recommendations

Since the study found out that male students are inclined into using the Internet for gaming, it is recommended that they should be reminded of the possible negative impacts of online gaming.

Conduct similar study but increase the sample size and involve students from other schools.

Conduct further investigation by relating the Internet usage to the academic performance of the students.

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